

Effectiveness of Aerogen Solo Nebulization on respiratory parameters among children diagnosed with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in Paediatric Intensive Care Unit of selected hospitals of city

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Received: Sep 15, 2025

Accepted: Oct 07, 2025

Published: Oct 15, 2025

ABSTRACT

Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) are a leading cause of morbidity and hospitalization among children, particularly in critical care settings. Prompt intervention using effective aerosol therapy is essential to improve respiratory outcomes. Aerogen solo nebulization is an advanced aerosol delivery system that may enhance drug deposition in the lungs and accelerate clinical improvement.

Objective: To assess the effectiveness of aerogen solo nebulization on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in paediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.

Methods: A quasi-experimental pre-test post-test control group design was adopted. The study included 30 children aged 5 to 10 years, divided into an experimental group (n = 15) and a control group (n = 15). Both groups received standard treatment, while the experimental group was additionally administered Aerogen solo nebulization. Pre- and post-intervention respiratory parameters including respiratory rate, tidal volume, peak pressure, oxygen saturation, and end-tidal CO₂ were recorded. Statistical analyses included paired *t*-test, independent *t*-test, and Fisher's exact test.

Results: The experimental group demonstrated significant post-intervention improvement in respiratory parameters. Oxygen saturation normalized in 100% of participants, tidal volume and peak pressure in 60%, and ET_{CO₂} in 66.7%. The mean respiratory score improved from 1.1 to 3.7 ($t = 9.5, p < 0.05$). In contrast, the control group showed minimal improvement with a mean score change of 1. The between-group difference was statistically significant ($t = 3.4, p < 0.05$). No significant association was found between respiratory improvement and demographic variables.

Conclusion: Aerogen solo nebulization significantly improves respiratory parameters in children with LRTI and can be considered an effective and safe intervention in pediatric intensive care settings.

Keywords: *Arogen solo, nebulization, lower respiratory tract infection, pediatric intensive care, respiratory parameters.*

INTRODUCTION:

The most common illnesses in babies and children are respiratory infections, including the common cold, acute rhinosinusitis, acute otitis media, flu-like illnesses, acute bronchitis and pneumonia. Despite being largely harmless, they have a significant negative impact on society and are a leading source of morbidity and mortality worldwide. They are further divided into two categories Lower Respiratory infections and lower respiratory infections. The most common symptoms and signs in these children are cough and increased respiratory rate. The presence of lower chest retraction indicates a more serious disease. The most common causes of LRI are viruses, and RSV is the most important cause among other viruses. In 2010, WHO recognized respiratory diseases as the second leading cause of death for children under five. According to WHO, pneumonia is one of the three leading causes of death in newborns. In 2008, pneumonia was diagnosed in about 156 million children (151 million in developing countries and 5 million in developed countries) and caused 1.4 million deaths (28-34% of all under-five deaths).

These disorders can range from moderate to life-threatening, requiring hospitalization and emergency treatment. To aerosolize medications, a wide range of devices such as pressurized metered dose inhalers and nebulizers are used, and the interactions between these devices and lung delivery are of great interest in study. Conventional (breath-actuated (BAN), breath-enhanced (BEN), or constant-output) jet nebulizers. Aerosol therapy is a primary treatment for respiratory disorders such as bronchospasm, mucociliary clearance dysfunction, microbial infections, and inflammation during invasive mechanical ventilation.

OBJECTIVE

a. **Primary Objective:**

To assess the effectiveness of arogen solo nebulisation on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in paediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.

b. **Secondary Objectives:**

- To assess pre- interventional respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in paediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.

- To assess the effectiveness of arogen solo nebulisation on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in paediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.
- To find association between pre-test score with selected demographic variables

HYPOTHESIS

H₀- There is no significant effect of Arogen solo Nebulization on respiratory parameters among children diagnosed with Lower Respiratory tract infection. ($p = 0.05$)

H₁- There is significant effect of Arogen solo Nebulization on respiratory parameters among children diagnosed with Lower Respiratory tract infection. ($p = 0.05$)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The present study is Quantitative Research, Quasi experimental pretest posttest control group design. In this study, Researcher have adopted a Quantitative approach for the Effectiveness of Arogen Solo Nebulization on respiratory parameters among children diagnosed with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in Paediatric Intensive Care Unit of selected hospitals of city. 30 samples were selected 15 control and 15 Experimental by using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. The sample was chosen based on specific inclusion criteria from the selected hospitals. The research tool comprised demographic data and a self-prepared observational checklist for respiratory parameters. An informed consent form regarding their willingness to participate in the study had to be signed by the parents of each willing participants were given to the parents. Before any data was collected, the researcher allayed the parents concern about the study. The demographic information of the child using standardized questionnaires were collected by the researcher and additionally the researcher assessed the effectiveness of arogen solo nebulization on respiratory parameters by using self-prepared observational checklist. To enlighten the parents with their children's rights. With every sample, the researcher had taken the necessary amount of time where in the willingness of each sample was given preference.

Results

SECTION I

Description of samples based on their demographic characteristics.

Age : In experimental and control group, 73.3% of the children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in paediatric intensive care unit had age 5 to 7 years and 26.7% of them had age 7.1 to 10 years.

Gender: In experimental and control group, 60% them were males and 40% of them were females.

Diagnosis: In experimental group, 53.3% of them were diagnosed with pneumonia, 40% of them were diagnosed with bronchiolitis and 6.7% of them were diagnosed with some other disease.

Day on ventilator: In experimental group, 20% of them were on ventilator for one day, 60% of them were on ventilator for two days and 20% of them were on ventilator for three days. In control group, 6.7% of them were on ventilator for one day, 40% of them were on ventilator for two days, 46.7% of them were on ventilator for three days and 6.7% of them were on ventilator for four days.

Day of nebulization : In experimental group, 33.3% of them were nebulized for one day and 66.7% of them were nebulized for 2 days. In control group, 20% of them had nebulization for 2 days and 80% of them had nebulization for three days.

Medicine: In experimental and control group, 40% of them had BUDECORT and 60% of them had ASTHALIN.

Section II

Analysis of data related to pre- interventional respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.

Table 2: Pre- interventional respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.

In experimental group, all of children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit had moderate depression. In control group, 13.3% of them had mild depression and 86.7% of them had moderate depression.

Section III

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of aerogen solo nebulization on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city

Table 3: Effectiveness of aerogen solo nebulization on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit of selected hospitals of city.

In experimental group, in pretest, all of children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit had moderate depression. In posttest, 26.7% of them did not had depression, 60% of them had mild depression and 13.3% of them had moderate depression. In control group, in pretest, 13.3% of them had mild depression and 86.7% of them had moderate depression. In posttest, 6.7% of them did not had depression, 46.7% of them had mild depression, 40% of them had moderate depression and 6.7% of them had severe depression. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the depression among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit.

Table 4: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of aerogen solo nebulization on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit.

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of aerogen solo nebulization on respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit. Average depression score in pretest was 1.1 which increased to 3.7 in posttest. T-value for this test was 9.5 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (greater than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average depression score in posttest was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the aerogen solo nebulization is significantly effective

in improving the respiratory status among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit.

Table 5: Two sample t-test for the comparison of change in respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit in experimental and control group.

Group	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Experimental	2.6	1.1	3.4	28	0.001
Control	1.0	1.5			

Researcher applied paired t-test for the for the comparison of change in respiratory parameters among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit in experimental and control group. Average change in depression score in experimental group was 2.6 which was 1 in control group. T-value for this test was 3.4 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (greater than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average increase in respiratory score was significantly more in experimental group than that in control group. It is evident that the aerogen solo nebulization is significantly effective in improving the respiratory status among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in pediatric intensive care unit.

Item analysis

In experimental group, in pretest 93.3% of them and in posttest 86.7% of them had normal respiratory rate. In control group, in pretest 93.3% of them and in posttest 80% of them had normal respiratory rate. In experimental group, in pretest none of them and in posttest 60% of them had normal peak pressure. In control group, in pretest 13.3% of them and in posttest 40% of them had normal respiratory rate. In experimental group, in pretest 6.7% of them and in posttest 60% of them had normal tidal volume. In control group, in pretest 26.7% of them and in posttest 26.7% of them had normal tidal volume. In experimental group, in pretest none of them and in posttest all of them had normal oxygen saturation. In control group, in pretest 13.3% of them and in posttest 60% of them had normal oxygen saturation. In experimental group, in pretest 6.7% of them and in posttest 66.7% of them had normal ET CO₂. In control group, in pretest 13.3% of them and in posttest 40% of them had normal ET CO₂. This indicates that the respiratory parameters improved remarkably after the aerogen solo nebulization in experimental group.

Respiratory parameter	Experimental				Control			
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Respiratory rate	14	93.3%	13	86.7%	14	93.3%	12	80.0%
Peak pressure	0	0.0%	9	60.0%	2	13.3%	6	40.0%
Tidal volume	1	6.7%	9	60.0%	4	26.7%	4	26.7%
Oxygen saturation	0	0.0%	15	100.0%	2	13.3%	9	60.0%
ET CO ₂	1	6.7%	10	66.7%	2	13.3%	6	40.0%

Section IV

Analysis of data related to association between pre-test score with selected demographic variables

Table 7: Fisher's exact test for the association between pre-test score with selected demographic variables

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables were found to have significant association with the respiratory depression among children with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in paediatric intensive care unit.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the study Effectiveness of Aerogen Solo Nebulization on respiratory parameters among children diagnosed with lower respiratory tract infection admitted in Paediatric Intensive Care Unit of selected hospitals of city. The study was based on the J. W. Kennys Open system model. It study made use of the Quasi –experimental pre-test post-test control group design descriptive. The study population consisted of children who were Admitted in selected hospitals of city. A total of 30 samples were taken 15 for experimental and 15 for control with the

Non probability purposive sampling technique. For generating necessary data. content validation was done by 13 experts form different filed. The data was collected from 23/12/2024 to 11/01/2025. Sample were selected according to the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteriathus parents were introduced by the investigator. Explained the purpose of the study and assured about the confidentiality of the information between the investigator and the respondent. Before Data Collection consent was taken from the parent. Data was collected from 30 samples from selected hospitals of city. Findings were recorded according to the tool. The data was gathered using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Acknowledgement: The researcher would like to acknowledge the ethical committee and authorities of selected hospitals and all the participants for their support in the study.

Conflict of interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

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